

Incidence of infection of trematode genus *Azygia looss*, 1899 parasitic in freshwater fish *Channa punctatus*

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation deals with the incidence of infection of Trematode *A. angusticauda* by Stafford, 1904 parasitizing of *Channa punctatus* from different localities of Nanded District (M.S.) India during February, 2014 to January, 2015. The high prevalence of trematode parasites were occurred in Summer (79.16 %) followed by Winter (62.50 %) whereas infection was low in monsoon (39.58%).

Keywords: *A. angusticauda* Stafford, 1904, *Channa punctatus*, Incidence of infection, Nanded

INTRODUCTION

Helminth parasite infection are among the most common parasitic infection of humans worldwide and are now well recognized as an important public health problem both in developing and developed countries. Fish play an important role in economy. Mortality of fishes occurs due to heavy infestation of helminth parasites. Notable contribution made in population dynamics of helminth parasites by Dobson, (1961& 1965); Dogiel et. al., (1954); Johnson, (1964); Anderson, (1974); Kenddey, (1975) & Moller et. al., (1995) Poulin, R. (1995), Rajeshwar Rao (1983) and Rohde, (1993). Results of present study, therefore, are expected to be helpful for future research on helminth parasites of freshwater fishes in this area. Keeping in view, importance of trematode infections of freshwater fish, the present study was designed to evaluate the prevalence of trematode genus *Azygia* Looss, 1899 parasitizing freshwater fish *Channa punctatus*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the present study, *Channa punctatus*, were examined for Trematode infection during the period of February, 2014 to January, 2015 from different localities of Nanded District, Maharashtra State India. Trematodes were collected, preserved in hot 4% formalin, dehydrated in various alcoholic grades, stained with Borax carmine, cleared in xylene and mounted in D.P.X. These Trematodes were prepared for identification by standard methods. On taxonomic observations identified trematode is *A.angusticauda* Stafford, 1904. Obtained data were recorded; processed for study of incidence of infection.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of present studies on incidence of infection of cestode, *A.angusticauda* Stafford, 1904 from *Channa punctatus* are presented in Table-1 & Figure-1.

Table-1. Incidence of infection of *A.angusticauda* Stafford, 1904 from *Channa punctatus* during February, 2014 to January, 2015.

Seasons	Number of host Examined	Number of host Infected & their Prevalence	Number of parasites collected
Summer (Feb.,2014-May,2014)	48	38 (79.16 %)	46
Monsoon (June, 2014 –Sept., 2014)	48	19 (39.58%)	24
Winter (Oct.,2014- Jan., 2015)	48	30 (62.50 %)	35

Figure-1. Incidence of infection of *A.angusticauda* Stafford, 1904 from *Channa punctatus* during February, 2014 to January, 2015.

The incidence of infection of *A.angusticauda* Stafford, 1904 were recorded in Summer (79.16 %) followed by Winter (62.50 %) whereas infection was low in monsoon (39.58%).

Kennedy C.R. (1976) reported temperature; humidity, rainfall, feeding habits of host, availability of infective host and parasite maturation are responsible for influencing the parasitic infections. Feeding activity of the host is reason for seasonal fluctuation of infections (Pennuyick, 1973). Nair and Nadakal (1981) explained retarded growth, decreased egg production, reduced weight gain, significant haemoglobin depression due to infections of cestode parasites in chickens. Jadhav and Bhure, (2006) noticed high temperature, low rainfall and sufficient moisture were necessary for development of parasite.

Results of present study are in agreement with Bhure et. al. (2010) reported high incidence (51.78%), intensity (1.18%) and density (0.613%) of *Rhabdocona* sp. in summer followed by winter and rainy season. Farhaduzzaman et.al. (2010) and Laxma Reddy, B and Benarjee, G (2014) studied Prevalence of Parasites in the Indian Major Carp, *Labeo rohita* (Hamilton) in Rajshahi, Bangladesh and noticed highest prevalence (75%) and mean density (10.44) of parasites were found in the month of December and lowest (20%) in the month of February. Shahin et.al., 2011 studied prevalence of Chicken Cestodiasis in Egypt and reported highest incidence in summer 5.54% and Autumn 5.6% and lowest incidence during Winter 3.3% and Spring 2.2%. Bhure et al., 2013 studied diversity and prevalence of avian cestodes and reported high prevalence in summer where as

low in monsoon season. Bhure et.al. (2013) and Himansu Bhusan Mahananda, (2014) studied seasonal variation of Caryophyllidean tapeworms, which showed maximum infection in winter (71.66%) followed by summer (43.33%) whereas lower infection in monsoon (15.00%). Bhure and Nanware, (2014) reported high incidence of infection of *Cotugnia dignopora*, *Cotugnia diamarae* and *Raillietina (R.) domestica* in summer (75%, 67.85 % & 71.42%) followed by winter (60%, 52 % & 48%) whereas low infections in monsoon season (38.09%, 33.33% & 38.09%). Bhure and Nanware, 2014 recorded high incidence of infection of *Senga sp.*, *Gangesia sp.*, *Proteocephalus sp.* infected to *Channa sp.* was in summer (76.66 %, 73.33 % & 70.00 %) followed by winter (65.21 %, 52.17% & 56.52%) whereas infection was low in monsoon (36.84%, 26.31% & 31.57%). Bhure et.al., 2014 studied prevalence of helminth parasites of Freshwater fish *Mastacembelus armatus* from Nanded Region and noticed high incidence of infections were recorded in summer (Feb., 2014-May, 2014) followed by winter (Oct., 2013- Jan., 2014) where as low in monsoon (June, 2013 – Sept., 2013).

Recorded data of present study shows high incidence of infections of trematode was in summer followed by winter where as low in monsoon due to environmental factors and feeding habitat influence the seasonality of parasitic infection either directly or indirectly.

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